

Apparent molar volumes and adiabatic compressibilities of L-glycine in aqueous solutions of (CH₃)₄NI, NaBr and NaI at 298.15 K^ψ

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The densities and sound speeds of L-glycine in aqueous (CH₃)₄NI, NaBr and NaI are reported at 298.15 K. These data are used to derive apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} and compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$. Partial molar volumes V_{ϕ}^0 and partial molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}^0$ of L-glycine at infinite dilution were evaluated. These values are required for calculating hydration number n_H of L-glycine. Transfer volumes ΔV_{ϕ}^0 and transfer adiabatic compressibilities $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ at infinite dilution from water to aqueous electrolyte solutions have been calculated. Transfer parameters have been interpreted in terms of solute-solute interactions on the basis of a cosphere overlap model.

It is well known that salt solutions have large effects on the solubility behavior of amino acids¹. In the literature²⁻¹⁰ there are some experimental and theoretical reports about the effect of various salts on amino acids. In fact, salts interact directly with the zwitterionic centre of the amino acids and bring about change in its hydration or interactive behavior in solutions. Therefore, in order to understand the behavior of amino acids in concentrated salt solutions, we have studied the thermodynamic parameters, partial molar volumes and adiabatic compressibilities, for L-glycine in aqueous (CH₃)₄NI, NaBr and NaI solutions at 298.15 K.

Results and discussion

The measured densities ρ and sound speeds u are listed in Table 1 at different concentrations of L-glycine and salts.

The apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ and the apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} were calculated from the sound speed and the solution density results with the following equations :

$$K_{\phi,s} = M \cdot \beta_S / \rho - \{ 1000 \cdot (\beta_{S,0} \cdot \rho - \beta_S \cdot \rho_0) / m \cdot \rho \cdot \rho_0 \} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{\phi} = M / \rho - \{ 1000 \cdot (\rho - \rho_0) / m \cdot \rho \cdot \rho_0 \} \quad (2)$$

where m is the molality (mol kg⁻¹) of the solution, M is the relative molar mass of the solute (kg mol⁻¹) and ρ_0 , ρ , $\beta_{S,0}$ and β_S are the densities and coefficient of adiabatic compressibilities of pure solvent and solution, respectively. The resulting values of the apparent molar volumes V_{ϕ} , adiabatic compressibilities $K_{\phi,s}$ and the molal concentrations m of L-glycine in different concentrations of salts at

298.15 K are included in Table 1.

The coefficients of adiabatic compressibility β_S of the solute was determined from the sound speed u and density ρ data by using the relation :

$$\beta_S = 1 / (u^2 \cdot \rho) \quad (3)$$

The variation of apparent molar quantities with molality can be adequately represented by the relation :

$$Y_{\phi} = Y_{\phi}^0 + S_Q \cdot m \quad (4)$$

where Y_{ϕ}^0 (Y_{ϕ}^0 denotes V_{ϕ}^0 or $K_{\phi,s}^0$) is the limiting value of the apparent molar property (equal to the partial molar property at infinite dilution) and S_Q (S_Q denotes S_V or S_K) is the experimental or limiting slope. Eq. (4) was fitted to our experimental V_{ϕ} and $K_{\phi,s}$ values in different electrolyte solutions by the method of least squares to evaluate the infinite dilution partial molar volume V_{ϕ}^0 and adiabatic compressibility $K_{\phi,s}^0$. The values of V_{ϕ}^0 , $K_{\phi,s}^0$, S_V and S_K for L-glycine at 298.15 K are given in Table 2 along with the standard errors. The experimental values of V_{ϕ}^0 and $K_{\phi,s}^0$ for L-glycine in aqueous salt solutions are higher than the corresponding values in water reported in our previous papers^{11,12}.

The partial molar volumes of transfer ΔV_{ϕ}^0 and partial molar adiabatic compressibilities of transfer $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ from water to aqueous salt solutions have been calculated from equation :

$$\Delta Y_{\phi}^0 = Y_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in aqueous salt solution)} - Y_{\phi}^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (5)$$

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Table 1. Densities, ρ , speeds of sound, u , apparent molar volumes, V_{ϕ} , and apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities, $K_{\phi,s}$ of L-glycine in aqueous solutions of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$, NaBr and NaI at 298.15 K

(mol kg ⁻¹)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$V_{\phi} \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	m (mol kg ⁻¹)	u (m s ⁻¹)	$K_{\phi,s} \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)
0.05 mol kg ⁻¹ $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$					
0.00000	1.00395	—	0.00000	1498.1	—
0.50303	1.01757	47.27	0.49788	1523.5	-20.55
0.69978	1.02290	47.02	0.69887	1533.5	-20.48
0.89638	1.02822	46.78	0.89545	1543.0	-20.14
1.09922	1.03375	46.50	1.09881	1552.4	-19.75
1.29865	1.03911	46.29	1.28248	1560.8	-19.43
1.48902	1.04427	46.06	1.47820	1569.5	-19.06
0.2 mol kg ⁻¹ $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$					
0.00000	1.01439	—	0.00000	1501.5	—
0.50052	1.02796	47.03	0.53881	1529.2	-20.17
0.69906	1.03334	46.79	0.69753	1536.9	-19.83
0.90300	1.03887	46.54	0.90426	1547.0	-19.54
1.11593	1.04464	46.28	1.08171	1555.3	-19.19
1.27588	1.04898	46.09	1.27766	1564.4	-18.93
1.49863	1.05502	45.82	1.48678	1573.9	-18.59
0.05 mol kg ⁻¹ NaBr					
0.00000	1.00405	—	0.00000	1497.4	—
0.49918	1.01758	47.24	0.49589	1523.3	-19.52
0.69119	1.02278	47.01	0.69806	1537.2	-19.33
0.89914	1.02842	46.75	0.91811	1543.8	-19.31
1.10629	1.03404	46.49	1.12050	1553.2	-19.14
1.30940	1.03943	46.33	1.29863	1561.5	-19.01
1.49139	1.04437	46.10	1.51039	1570.9	-18.65
0.2 mol kg ⁻¹ NaBr					
0.00000	1.01560	—	0.00000	1501.6	—
0.49300	1.02876	47.42	0.50077	1527.4	-20.07
0.70248	1.03435	47.17	0.69977	1537.2	-19.61
0.89533	1.03950	46.93	0.91944	1547.8	-19.14
1.10431	1.04508	46.68	1.12146	1557.1	-18.77
1.31964	1.05077	46.47	1.30471	1565.6	-18.44
1.48788	1.05527	46.26	1.51084	1574.8	-18.15
0.05 mol kg ⁻¹ NaI					
0.00000	1.00565	—	0.00000	1496.0	—
0.50485	1.01930	47.27	0.48806	1521.3	-20.23
0.70050	1.02459	47.03	0.69247	1531.3	-19.99
0.90740	1.03018	46.78	0.90754	1541.7	-19.76
1.10523	1.03553	46.53	1.10417	1551.0	-19.58
1.28518	1.04049	46.24	1.29600	1559.9	-19.30
1.50393	1.04632	46.05	1.51599	1569.6	-18.93

0.2 mol kg ⁻¹ NaI					
0.00000	1.02165	–	0.00000	1494.8	–
0.49538	1.03499	47.07	0.48626	1520.4	–19.68
0.70761	1.04071	46.80	0.68305	1530.4	–19.51
0.89983	1.04587	46.59	0.89204	1540.7	–19.36
1.10825	1.05149	46.33	1.09516	1550.3	–19.07
1.30231	1.05683	46.01	1.27854	1558.9	–18.83
1.50416	1.06216	45.86	1.52467	1570.1	–18.42

Table 2. Limiting partial molar volumes, V_{ϕ}^0 , limiting partial molar adiabatic compressibilities, $K_{\phi,s}^0$, experimental slopes, S_V and S_K , transfer volumes, ΔV_{ϕ}^0 , and transfer adiabatic compressibilities, $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$, of L-glycine in aqueous solutions of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$, NaBr and NaI at 298.15 K

m_B (mol kg ⁻¹)	$V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$S_V \times 10^6$ (m ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})	$K_{\phi,s}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)	$S_K \times 10^6$ (kg m ³ mol ⁻² GPa ⁻¹)	$\Delta V_{\phi}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0 \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ GPa ⁻¹)
(CH_3) ₄ NI						
0.05	47.88 (±0.02)	–1.23 (±0.02)	–21.49 (±0.13)	1.60 (±0.13)	4.69	4.48
0.2	47.64 (±0.00)	–1.21 (±0.00)	–21.01 (±0.05)	1.64 (±0.05)	4.45	4.96
NaBr						
0.05	47.79 (±0.04)	–1.14 (±0.03)	–19.94 (±0.12)	0.77 (±0.11)	4.60	6.03
0.2	47.98 (±0.02)	–1.16 (±0.02)	–20.96 (±0.08)	1.91 (±0.08)	4.79	5.01
NaI						
0.05	47.91 (±0.04)	–1.25 (±0.04)	–20.86 (±0.07)	1.22 (±0.07)	4.72	5.11
0.2	47.68 (±0.05)	–1.23 (±0.05)	–20.34 (±0.10)	1.21 (±0.09)	4.49	5.63

Foot note : Parentheses indicate standard errors; V_{ϕ}^0 and $K_{\phi,s}^0$ values for (L-glycine + water) are 43.19×10^{-6} m³ mol⁻¹(11) and -25.97×10^{-6} m³ mol⁻¹ GPa⁻¹(12); m_B denotes the concentration of the salt.

where Y_{ϕ}^0 denotes V_{ϕ}^0 or $K_{\phi,s}^0$ and the values are listed in Table 2. As can be seen in Table 2 that the V_{ϕ}^0 values for L-glycine are positive whereas the $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values are negative in aqueous salt solutions at 298.15 K. It is found that V_{ϕ}^0 increases with increasing concentration of NaBr in solutions whereas it decreases with increasing $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$ and NaI concentrations but reverse is the case with $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values. It indicates that the solute-cosolute interactions is higher with NaBr at high concentrations than with $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$ and NaI.

The $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values increase with the concentration of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$ and NaI except with NaBr. The more positive values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ for L-glycine indicate the dominance of the interactions involving the charged centers NH_3^+ and COO^- . That is, the interactions between the salts and the zwitterionic centre of L-glycine. It may be recalled that the zwitterionic form of an amino acid has its hydrophilic hydration at the zwitterionic ends and hydrophobic hydration at the hydrocarbon skeleton. The hydrated cation (Na^+ / $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$) overlap the hydrated $-\text{COO}^-$ and the hydrated anion (Br^-/I^-) overlap the hydrated $-\text{NH}_3^+$ end of L-glycine. The overall effect is that the overlap of cospheres of two

opposite charged ionic species relaxes some solvation water to bulk, giving rise to positive values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 .

Table 2 shows that the variations in ΔV_{ϕ}^0 or $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ with cation or anion size are not very important. Again for small ions like Na^+ , where ionic charge is shielded by heavy solvation sheath or for larger ions like I^- where charge density is small resulting in negative hydration. This is quite evident from the small values of ΔV_{ϕ}^0 for L-glycine. The $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values for L-glycine in salt solutions are reported in Table 2. With the increase in concentration of salts, there is a decrease in the hydrogen-bonded network of water molecules in the solvation sphere, that is, electrostriction decreases and the structure-making tendency of the ion increases. As a result, the electrostricted water is much less compressible than the bulk water and leads to a large decrease in the compressibility with increase in salt concentration. Thus, $K_{\phi,s}^0$ values are negative and $\Delta K_{\phi,s}^0$ values are positive for L-glycine. This is important in case of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$ and NaI.

Franks *et al.*¹³ have pointed out that the partial molar volume of a non-electrolyte at infinite dilution is a combination of two factors, viz. the intrinsic molar volume of the non-hydrated solute V_{int} and the volume changes due

to its interactions with the solvent V_S :

$$V_{\phi}^0 = V_{\text{int}} + V_S \quad (6)$$

The intrinsic volume has been considered to be made up of two types of contributions^{14,15} :

$$V_{\text{int}} = V_{v,w} + V_{\text{void}} \quad (7)$$

where $V_{v,w}$ is van der Waals volume^{16a} and V_{void} is the volume associated with the void or empty spaces^{16b} present therein. For electrolytes and zwitterionic solutes, this equation was modified by Shahidi *et al.*¹⁴ in order to evaluate the contribution of a solute molecule towards its partial molar volume as :

$$V_{\phi}^0 = V_{v,w} + V_{\text{void}} - V_{\text{shrinkage}} \quad (8)$$

where $V_{\text{shrinkage}}$ is the volume due to shrinkage. This is produced by the interaction of hydrogen bonding sites present in the solute with water molecules. If we assume that $V_{v,w}$ and V_{void} have the same magnitudes in water and aqueous salt solutions, the positive ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values of L-glycine can be explained to result from the decrease in $V_{\text{shrinkage}}$ in presence of salts in aqueous solutions. Because of stronger interactions occur between COO^- and $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ and NH_3^+ and Br^-/I^- centers of L-glycine, the electrostriction of the neighboring water molecules due to these charge centers will be reduced, in the presence of salts, thereby causing a decrease in $V_{\text{shrinkage}}$. If one assumes these salts to be structure breaker, the above observation indicates that the structure-breaking tendency of these salts decreases^{17,18} due to its interaction with L-glycine molecule. In other words, some hydrogen-bonded network of water molecules in the solvation sphere may be released as bulk water in the presence of salts. It brings out the increase in the volume of the solvent, thereby reducing the strong interactions between L-glycine and water. This will also lead to a positive volume of transfer¹⁹ which arises due to solute-cosolute interactions.

The ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values can also be explained on the basis of the cosphere overlap model^{20,21} in terms of solute-cosolute interactions. According to this model, hydrophilic (Br^-/I^- or $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$) – ionic (NH_3^+ or COO^-) group interactions contribute positively, whereas hydrophilic (Br^-/I^- or $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$) – hydrophobic ($-\text{CH}_2$) group interactions contribute negatively to the ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values. Therefore, the significantly positive ΔV_{ϕ}^0 values observed in the present study suggest the dominance of the former type of interactions over the latter.

One may approximate that the cosphere of $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ is perturbed by its proximity to the cosphere

regions of the COO^- group and the $-\text{CH}_2$ chain or Br^-/I^- is perturbed by NH_3^+ ion. The perturbation in the cosphere of the $-\text{CH}_2$ part of L-glycine will not increase so much, since the $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ will tend to prefer to be in the proximity of the COO^- end of the L-glycine molecule. The same general argument can also be applied to the Br^-/I^- ion interaction. In this case, one can imagine that the Br^-/I^- ion would tend to stay in the proximity of the $-\text{NH}_3^+$ group rather than the $-\text{COO}^-$ group. The overall effect is that the sum of the interactions of the $\text{Na}^+(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ ion with L-glycine and the Br^-/I^- ion with L-glycine are predominant over the L-glycine or salt-water interactions throughout the concentration range of the salt.

The partial molar volume of the amino acid can be examined by a simple model²² :

$$V_{\phi}^0(\text{amino acid}) = V_{\phi}^0(\text{int}) + V_{\phi}^0(\text{elect}) \quad (9)$$

where $V_{\phi}^0(\text{elect})$ is the electrostriction partial molar volume due to the hydration of the amino acid and can be estimated from experimentally measured values of $V_{\phi}^0(\text{amino acid})$, and $V_{\phi}^0(\text{int})$ is the intrinsic partial molar volume of the amino acid and has been calculated from the following expressions²² :

$$V_{\phi}^0(\text{int}) = (0.7/0.634) V_{\phi}^0(\text{cryst}) \quad \text{and} \quad (10)$$

$$V_{\phi}^0(\text{int}) = (0.7/0.6) V_{\phi}^0(\text{cryst}) \quad (11)$$

where $V_{\phi}^0(\text{cryst}) (= \text{mol. wt.}/d_{\text{cryst}})$ is the crystal molar volume, 0.7 is the packing density for molecules in organic crystals and 0.634 is the packing density for random packing spheres. The values of $V_{\phi}^0(\text{int})$ of L-glycine have been estimated from eqs. (10–11) using d_{cryst} values for glycine (1.598 g cm^{-3}) taken from the work of Berlin and Pallansch²³.

The change in volume due to electrostriction can be related to the number of water molecules n_{H} hydrated to the amino acid by^{24,25} :

$$n_{\text{H}} = V_{\phi}^0(\text{elect}) / (V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0) \quad (12)$$

where $V_{\phi,e}^0$ is the molar volume of electrostricted water and $V_{\phi,b}^0$ is the molar volume of bulk water ($18.069 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K). The reported value²² of $(V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0)$ is $\approx -3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K. Using the value of $(V_{\phi,e}^0 - V_{\phi,b}^0)$ and the values of $V_{\phi}^0(\text{elect})$, calculated from both the two methods, the n_{H} values were estimated from eq. (12) and are given in Table 3.

Further, the number of water molecules n_{H} hydrated to the amino acids were calculated by using the method given by Millero *et al.*^{22,26} :

$$n_H = -K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect})/V_{\phi,b}^0 \cdot K_{s,b}^0 \quad (13)$$

where $K_{s,b}^0$ is the isothermal compressibility of bulk water. The value of $V_{\phi,b}^0 \cdot K_{s,b}^0$ is $\approx 0.81 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ GPa}^{-1}$. The electrostriction partial molar compressibility $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect})$ can be calculated from the experimentally measured values of $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid})$ from :

$$K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect}) = K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid}) - K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \quad (14)$$

where $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int})^{22,27} = K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{isomer})$ for glycine ($2.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ GPa}^{-1}$). Since one would expect $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int})$ to be small and it is less than $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ GPa}^{-1}$ for ionic crystals and many dissolved organic solutes in water²². So, one can assume $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \approx 0$. Therefore, for $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{int}) \approx 0$, eq. (14) becomes :

$$K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect}) = K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{amino acid}) \quad (15)$$

The values of n_H calculated from eq. (13) using the $K_{\phi,s}^0(\text{elect})$ values determined by these two methods are also given in Table 3. The values of n_H for L-glycine in presence of these salts are less than in water¹². The values of n_H estimated from compressibility data using eqs. (14, 15) are in reasonable agreement. These values are higher than the values calculated from volume data.

Table 3. Hydration number, n_H , for L-glycine in aqueous solutions of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$, NaBr and NaI at 298.15 K

m_B (mol kg ⁻¹)	n_H			
	From volume		From compressibility	
	Using eq. (11)	Using eq. (10)	Using eq. (14)	Using eq. (15)
	$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$			
0.05	2.10	1.21	3.01	2.67
0.2	2.17	1.28	2.95	2.61
	NaBr			
0.05	2.13	1.24	2.81	2.48
0.2	2.07	1.18	2.94	2.60
	NaI			
0.05	2.09	1.20	2.93	2.59
0.2	2.16	1.27	2.86	2.53

Experimental

L-Glycine (A.R.) was crystallized twice from ethanol-water mixture. The material was used after drying at 100° for 6 h and then under vacuum over silica gel at room temperature for a minimum of 24 h. The salts used in this study, $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$, NaBr and NaI were used after drying at 250° for 3 h and then in a vacuo over P_2O_5 at room temperature for a minimum of 48 h. Water used in these ex-

periments was deionized and distilled, and was degassed prior to making solutions. Salt solutions (0.05 and 0.2 mol kg⁻¹) were prepared by mass and used on the day they were prepared. Solutions of L-glycine (0.5–1.5 mol kg⁻¹) were made by mass on the molality concentration scale with a precision of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g}$ on a Dhona balance (India, Model 200 D). Uncertainties in solution concentration were estimated at $\pm 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$ in calculations. All solutions were used within 12 h after preparation to minimize decomposition due to bacterial contamination.

The solution densities were measured using a single stem pycnometer having a total volume of 8 cm³ and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 0.1 cm. The details pertaining to calibration, experimental set up and working procedure have been previously described¹¹. An average of triplicate measurements were taken into account. Sufficient care was taken to avoid any air bubble entrapment. The reproducibility in the density measurements was better than $\pm 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The speeds of sound were measured at 4 MHz using a NUSONIC (Mapco, Model 6080) Velocimeter based on the sing-around technique²⁸ with a single transducer cell. The ultrasonic speeds at 298.15 K were directly obtained from the average round trip period of the ultrasonic wave in a fixed path length between the piezoelectric transducer and reflector. The maximal error of the sound speed relative to water ($1496.687 \text{ m s}^{-1}$)²⁹ is estimated to be less than 0.2 m s^{-1} . Further details concerning the apparatus, experimental set up and operational procedures^{30–32} have been given previously. All the measurements were carried out in a well-stirred water bath whose temperature was controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$.

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